

THE CHALLENGE OF CO-CREATION: HOW TO CONNECT TECHNOLOGIES AND COMMUNITIES IN AN ETHICAL WAY

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ABSTRACT

The contribution aims to reflect on the ethical issues and moral dilemmas related to the process of co-creation with communities in the technological domain. While there is a significant amount of literature dedicated to co-creation, the best or good enough practices of co-creating artificial intelligence and broader emerging technology solutions are yet to be established. Ethical aspects come to the forefront when working with members of vulnerable and marginalised communities, with the discussion not sufficiently presented in academic literature.

Deriving from empirical material accumulated while working on the CommuniCity Horizon Europe project, we argue for an incremental improvement approach to co-creation aimed at both learning from and improving processes, with findings continuously shared and updated for potential replication purposes. We also stress the dialectic nature of co-creation with communities: the experimental, learning part coexists with the ‘do no harm’ principle and the need for a strong moral framework and continuous ethical monitoring. While advocating for such an approach, we emphasise the essential character of a thoughtful and careful design and execution of processes.

KEYWORDS: ethics, technology, AI, city, community, vulnerability, co-creation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the scope of literature on co-creation, the specificity of co-creation in the technological domain has not been elaborated extensively, with attempts suggesting the need for a different approach to the issue itself when it comes to co-creating technological solutions with citizens (Jarke, 2021, p.203; Spuzic et al., 2016). Even more so, the existing literature lacks the focus on engagements with members of vulnerable and marginalised communities, where ethical aspects and risk mitigation have even more significance. The abovementioned factors together form an interesting setting in which practical experiences of co-creation fill the knowledge gap and, if successfully disseminated, give an impetus for replication attempts, and opportunities for new learnings to be derived, accumulated, and disseminated. This curious and challenging circle we propose to call the mechanism of *incremental improvement*.

Experimentation as an approach to urban challenges had been outlined in the preceding European projects, OrganiCity and SynchroniCity (Amaxilatis et al., 2019; Wilson, 2019). According to Brynskov et al. (2018, p.151), experimentation “proposes a methodology to engage stakeholders in a processual, solution-oriented and citizen-centric manner when addressing urban challenges and problems.”

The distinctive character of the approach proposed by this work is rooted in coexistence of the experimental foundation and ‘high stakes’ in the ethical domain, consequent to engagements with community members, especially when it concerns vulnerable and marginalised communities.

In this work we aim to reflect on ongoing experiences within CommuniCity Horizon Europe project as a source of empirical material for learnings on co-creation in the domain of artificial intelligence and broader new emerging technologies, with a focus on engaging disadvantaged communities.

2. COMMUNITY CONTEXT

The project draws on three rounds of open calls starting in the cities of Porto, Amsterdam and Helsinki and then ‘replicated’ in other European cities during the project timeframe of three years. In the beginning of the open call rounds, hosting cities announce societal challenges to which pilot proposals need to respond. Selected by independent jury members, awarded pilots aim to develop technological solutions tailored to the specific needs of local communities together with the members of those communities by means of co-creation. The overall aspiration of the project is to accumulate experiences and learnings on co-creation of targeted technological solutions with disadvantaged groups, to come up with replicable practices.

For the process of incremental improvement, it is important that the learnings that derive from both successes and failures are shared, reflected upon, with best and good enough practices replicated by other cities and communities, new learnings shared, the knowledge framework improved and updated. As community members are aimed to be the end users of technological solutions, their needs are meant to be at the heart of the process design. Without sincere interest and in-depth immersion in their life circumstances, methods, approaches, and know-how will likely remain formal tools. The project framework also has its limitations. For instance, each pilot period lasts five months within which the cooperating partners work towards a solution. The funding of €12500 is granted per winning pilot. Working and co-creating with members of disadvantaged communities in response to complicated and delicate challenges requires time and funding sufficient to run feasible pilots in which the ‘challenge owner’ (usually the municipality unit with corresponding expertise), community and technological provider can all advance. With learning accumulation being the main project objective, we can immediately spot a moral dilemma when concluding pilots with final implementable solutions is a desirable but not necessary situation, while engaged community members and ‘challenge owners’ put effort into working towards solutions. As a balancing act, concrete steps taken to progress with the solution, if not make it achievable in a short term, work towards a positive experience for all parties involved.

Successful and rewarding co-creation experiences require trust. It takes time to thoroughly assess the challenge before a thoughtful design process can begin, and this also limits the complexity of challenges that can be addressed in the pilot environment.

3. CO-CREATION IN THE CONTEXT

Co-creation processes are approached by a wide range of academic disciplines, including management and innovation studies that aim to give a structured overview of the issue rather than providing a conceptual framework. For instance, Rose et al. (2013, p.23) define co-creation as “an interactive, creative and social process between stakeholders.” Within the context of innovation studies, co-creation is seen as “open innovation with customers” (Rayna & Striukova, 2015, p.38). It “corresponds to the customer-related part of open innovation: ‘open innovating’ with consumers necessarily implies co-creating with them” (Rayna et al., 2015, p.2). While not explicitly mentioned in the project proposal, *the innovation part of our project is comprised by both technological and social innovation aspects, with an attempt to see them connected rather than exercised separately.* This is not the first European project comprising these, oftentimes viewed in silos, innovation vectors (Kohlgrüber et al., 2018, 2021; Wilson et al., 2019). The significant distinction is in attempt to connect social and technological domains in a mutually rewarding way, in bringing communities to the centre of the processes, in experimentation combined with high ethical ‘stakes’ consequent to conditions of vulnerability and marginalisation.

As suggested by the OECD report on co-creation (Rossi et al., 2020, p.1), “when co-creating a complex technological solution, the intermediary is involved in two complementary, often intertwined, but distinct processes that bring together organisations that demand technology and those that supply technological solutions.” In our project, the role of intermediaries has mostly been assigned to associations, mainly non-profit organisations that have established connections with vulnerable and marginalised communities. According to Rill and Hämäläinen (2018, p.2), the main foundational principle of co-creation as “harnessing the collective potential of groups can lead to breakthroughs wherein every participant is empowered.” The ‘empowerment’ wording is very interesting in application to co-creation in the technological domain. Digital disparity is a feature of the socio-technical landscape even in developed countries. It is a matter of uneven power, where actions to empower are crucial to bridge the growing gap. Knowledge and skills, starting with basic digital know-how, play a role in these power dynamics. New technologies can both empower and pose risks for vulnerable and marginalised communities, including the elderly, people with disabilities, long-term unemployed individuals, refugees, and those with lower incomes. The evolving landscape may bring positive changes on personal and community levels, but it could also worsen the circumstances. Moreover, there are both ‘objective’ and ‘subjective’ aspects. The latter represents how individuals ‘feel’ about new technologies: the presence of individual or collective anxieties around new emerging technologies may not necessarily relate to the factual side such as a disadvantageous position, bias, or discrimination. Instead, it may relate to the perception of rapid technological development working ‘against’ an individual or a group.

Conditions of vulnerability and marginalisation are discussed in a wide range of academic disciplines. According to Wrigley and Dawson (2016, p.203), the concept of vulnerability has not been defined clearly enough but it “indicates that an individual or group is thought to have a particular status that may adversely impact upon their well-being.” In this work, we use both words, ‘vulnerable’ and ‘marginalised’, to describe communities we aim to target in the project. The vector of these two human conditions differs, with vulnerability being an internal characteristic and marginalisation related to the ‘outside’ world, with a strong circumstantial connection to features of reality. The passive tense in the latter reflects such a connection and a negative influence of circumstances of the external world on the internal situation. The ‘disadvantaged’ may be seen as an umbrella term uniting these conditions while being a more neutral constatation of disparity.

To experiment with developing technological solutions for vulnerable and marginalised groups within the context and possibilities of a pilot, we suggest paying attention to the scope of the challenge and peculiarities of the particular group, outlining two variables – the vulnerability of the group and the sensitivity of the challenge. The more intense the conditions of vulnerability and marginalization are, the more sensitive the announced challenge is, the more time and effort are required from a technological party, the more is the need to ‘immerse’ in the target group and the challenge. Making authentic connections with communities requires an approach more sophisticated than traditional business and marketing tools aimed at engagement and co-creation. The experiment here plays not only a methodological role on a path of incremental improvement but is also necessary for the parties involved, including technological providers, as preliminary recommendations are not enough to fully understand and correctly perceive where the boundaries lie. Here we need to emphasize once more the dialectical relation between experiment and sensitive conditions within the project and pilots: while arguing for experiment aimed at the incremental improvement of co-creation practices, the more vulnerable the target group is and the more complex and sensitive the issues are, the greater is the chance of disappointment and failure, and the more effort we need to put into ethical consideration, both preliminary and continuous.

4. ETHICAL QUESTIONS

One of the ethical questions not yet sufficiently answered in the project is the ethical way to respond to the possible situation in which community members add value to the development of the solution but then will not be amongst the ones who benefit from this solution in its later development stage. The underlying reasons for such a situation may vary: in one of the examples from the city of Amsterdam, the piloting solution, despite multiple challenges on the way of this particular pilot implementation, is appreciated by the pilot host with an aim to sustain and utilise the solution beyond the piloting timeframe. The unexpected problem the pilot host faces at the end of the piloting period is the high maintenance cost of the solution making this aspiration not feasible, while having motivation and resources available but not matching with the costs and with alternative possibilities of spending these resources on direct activities supporting the 'target group' with regard to the same challenge. A similar obstacle is observed with pilots in Porto.

Another ethical challenge that has been 'spotted on' in the project is *the dilemma of 'co-creation with' and 'testing on'*. Does the line between the two exist, and if so, where should it be drawn? For example, if the proposed solution is an application that needs to be developed through new data coming from a vulnerable or marginalised community being 'fed' to this application, is this an example of co-creation or 'testing on'? One of the answers proposed is that the way the obtained data will be used determines the answer: one may use the data for improving or finalising a commercial solution or a solution tailored for these specific people, members of the 'target community'. When the latter happens, there is still an issue of the solution not being made available free of charge or at a reduced cost to those who tested it and helped it to evolve, as is suggested by the experience of Porto and Amsterdam.

In view of project partners who share a technological professional background, any technological project needs people and data, with technological solutions needed to be tested. From this standpoint, there is not much of a difference for the technological provider whether it is engaged in 'testing on' activities or co-creation activities, with the latter being more challenging and demanding. Both modalities though require the translation activities on the initial stage aimed to prepare the 'target group' for the engagement activities. Parties with the social innovation professional focus do outline the difference: in this view, by co-creation we should mean facilitating the setting where we can question the product itself and not the setting where the already designed product is presented to collect the feedback of community members. It should start and grow in a process of dialogue that demands a lot of time and effort. From this perspective, 'testing on' is not a negative term, but it is different from co-creation. Interestingly, this discussion had not been raised in projects preceding CommuniCity, such as SynchroniCity and OrganiCity, and it would be interesting to continue it further, also within the framework of incremental improvement of the processes.

The situation we wanted to avoid by all means is the 'aftertaste' of community members feeling 'used', exploited by pilot teams for the teams to develop commercial, 'for profit' solutions. Consequently, we saw the social innovation vector as leading while designing the open call and piloting processes. Many questions still do not have an unequivocal answer, this also includes the practicalities of approaching and motivating community members to participate in the project including the question of reward. For instance, the Amsterdam-based pilot hosts and intermediaries articulated the need for financial rewards assigned to community members engaged in co-creation and intermediaries themselves helping to connect with communities. Other partners pointed to the problems related to financial reward: while in technological domains such a reward is a usual practice, enabling communities to get access to final solutions is an incomparably more significant factor and motivation, so we need to put the effort in making this more feasible.

It is important to mention that the risks of disappointment and demotivation relate not only to communities but also to pilot hosts. In Amsterdam, pilot hosts belong to different structural units inside the City of Amsterdam. Their efforts start from the co-creation of challenges that are later announced by the City and to which the applicants need to respond. The motivation of pilot hosts derives from their practical interest in finding sustainable technological solutions for the existing needs. By them the project is seen as an instrument for tackling the objectives and finding practical solutions to significant problems. Then, at the end of the piloting period, the pilot host unexpectedly finds out that the solution, while being desirable to be procured, is too expensive. The disappointment and demotivation to put effort further in the next rounds of open calls may follow. The scenario when technological solutions are procured after piloting rounds is positive and desirable, it is the value added beyond the declared scope of the project and the factor raising its impact.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The vulnerable and marginalised community specificity, as well as the situation of power imbalance, lead to the necessity to prepare a minimal set of recommendations addressed to the technological providers on how to engage with communities. The points comprising the list below are developed inside the framework of the first piloting round, primarily based on piloting experiences of the City of Amsterdam (Khutsishvili, 2024):

1. Time and effort needed on the preparatory stage should not be underestimated.
2. Simplicity, clarity, evidence should be the core principles of all community engagement activities.
3. Reasoning in favour of mutual benefit (Why do we need to participate? What can we learn from each other? What is the significant and meaningful outcome we are putting effort towards?)
4. Keeping in mind the power imbalance. Trying to share ownership (of ongoing processes, of final solutions).
5. Diverging from the established practices of work. Adjusting not only the message but also the way of delivery (stepping out of the office space and going into 'the field'; emphasising the relatable points while keeping authentic).
6. Having a genuine interest in the community and its members. Imitating such an interest will not benefit any of the parties involved.
7. Being ready for initial attempts to fail and trying again.
8. Considering consulting with and/or involving in the processes the 'intermediaries' – people close and trusted by community members. For 'intermediaries' it may take less time to reach the community members. In Amsterdam and Porto, this was mostly the role of associations. Yet, in one of the pilots, the 'intermediary' individuals had been involved and paid by the pilot host to help to facilitate the trusted contact with a specific community of youth with criminal records and provide feedback on the pilot activities and the solution proposed by the pilot.
9. Having a vision of how the engagement should be designed in order to have a positive effect on the community is necessary from the very beginning.
10. Reflecting on the (potential) difference between 'co-creating with' and 'testing on', in the context of a particular community, challenge, and proposed solution.

In addition to the kick-off, midterm and concluding meetings, Amsterdam designed periodical meetings aimed to facilitate discussions, with guests separated during the sessions with regard to their 'professional' focus in a pilot, be it technological providers, associations, civil servants, or community members. The awarded pilot teams outlined points of reflection and suggestions for further open call and piloting process adjustment (Khutsishvili, 2024). Among those are:

1. The meaning as well as the definition of co-creation in the project may be unclear for a pilot team. The suggestion is to organise meetings on co-creation uniting all pilot teams at the start of the next rounds of piloting. During such a meeting, the project partners and different pilot teams could share their methods.
2. If a pilot takes place during summer, it is more difficult to establish the needed partnerships and engagement moments. In this case, it is proposed to extend the pilot duration.
3. For the success of the pilot, it is crucial that a technological provider thoroughly understands the target community, people's problems and needs.
4. Co-creation is not only a method required for the given project. It is also a useful tool to appeal to the community.
5. It is important to make sure that the open call is also announced in the target neighbourhood itself so that local technological companies which are likely to already understand the context can respond and participate.
6. The possibilities of involvement of community members on the very initial stage can be further explored. For instance, let the 'target' group read along with the proposals and thus give them a role in the jury.
7. It is crucial for a technological provider to be sure that the association they are teaming with has a solid contact with the target community. Otherwise, numerous problems will come on the way, and they will be difficult to overcome inside a limited piloting timeframe.
8. It is important for the teams to ensure that members of target communities are available for the engagement activities from the beginning of the pilot, otherwise time will be lost and the pilot may not be finished during the given timeframe.
9. Once the target community has joined, make sure you start co-creation activities quickly and don't wait too long, otherwise you may lose the motivation of people.
10. It is necessary to thoroughly explain to all parties involved, especially to technological providers, what is meant by co-creation and why it is important for the project as a whole and for the success of a particular pilot.
11. All parties should be aware that if the awarded team proposes the solution already existing in its technological portfolio to be 'tested on' a new audience, the vulnerable or marginalised community, such a solution can indeed be partly adapted to the needs of the specific community but there is no 'one fit for all', so such solutions may not always be suitable for the particular community.
12. Co-creation approaches must 'fit well' with the experiences of the target community.
13. For technological providers engagement with communities can be hard and time-consuming.
14. The open call information should be more detailed, with a focus on engagement and co-creation with communities, the resources required and possible challenges.

15. The jury needs to pay careful attention to the team's response to co-creation in the project proposal.
16. The more vulnerable the community is, the greater the chance that harm can be done if the expectations that have been raised are not met.
17. While engaging with community, it is important to 'take it seriously': listen well, gather the feedback carefully, explain and translate all steps well, even in cases of a difficult technological solution (for example, an animated video).
18. No stereotyping should take place. An equal non-hierarchical approach is necessary.
19. The translation challenge in its literal sense is something to be aware of. If the winning team is not based in the country where the pilot takes place, geographical and linguistic barriers can impact the engagement activities. Literal translation issues and co-creation in another language (English) than the official language of the country need to be further reflected on in the project.
20. There is a complex issue of financial remuneration of community members for their participation: according to some pilot hosts and intermediaries working 'in the field', community members put effort that is equal to effort put in regular work, so those efforts should be remunerated, this is also a matter of respectful and professional treatment. At the same time, and this is the point raised by a technological provider: if technological providers pay to test their products, would it lead to the situation when community members participate in co-creation just because of remuneration? In addition, another pilot team members quoted the member of target community who stated that he participates in the project "to help people, to work together towards a higher goal." This vector of shared experiences and motivation needs further reflection and discussion.

6. CONCLUSION

Co-creation activities aimed at the communities in question do not make piloting processes easier, quite the opposite. Yet, the opportunities for experimentation and learning accumulation enabled by such design are extremely valuable. To facilitate and conduct the related activities of community engagement activities in an ethical way, it is necessary to keep in mind the 'do no harm' principle, the power imbalance including the imbalance of professional, technological subject-related knowledge, and the general condition of belonging to a disadvantaged community.

The balancing act, as well as the risk mitigation, may be exercised by providing clear and honest communication including communication on the general aims and limitations of the project and a particular pilot. Encouraging dialogue on equal terms, aimed at 'de-objectivization' of the community and empowering its members from the very beginning of the engagement, is crucial.

Arguing for the incremental improvement approach, we emphasise the dialectical relationship between experimentation and community engagement, especially with vulnerable and marginalised communities being at the heart of the project. In our view, such a setting brings unprecedented analytical and research possibilities but also stresses the factor of responsibility and the ethical component. The learnings, in their broader sense, include not only successes but failures. At the same time, with communities being at the centre of the processes, not all failures are acceptable. Consequent efforts put in preliminary ethical consideration and continuous ethical monitoring and advise are required for running such projects.

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